

Studies on Oxalatostannates

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The masking of tin(IV) by oxalic acid finds use in analytical processes. The stepwise formation of tin oxalate $\text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$, and an oxalatotin(IV) acid $\text{H}_4[\text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_4]$, in aqueous solution was suggested for the above reaction¹. Of the two oxalatostannates known so far the potassium compound was formulated first as $\text{K}_2\text{SnO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and later as $\text{K}_2\text{Sn}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_7 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}^{2-}$, but its existence was doubted³. The other⁴ known oxalatostannate $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{N}]_2[\text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3]$, was isolated from non-aqueous medium, and its infrared and Raman spectra were reported. The present work was undertaken to resolve the controversial views on the potassium compound and to isolate various other oxalatotin compounds at different pH values from aqueous medium and study of the isolated products.

Results and Discussion

The chemical compositions of the various isolated oxalatostannates show $\text{Sn}^{4+} : \text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ ratios ranging from 1 : 2 to 1 : 4. The results demonstrate that the number of oxalato groups attached to Sn^{IV} increases with the increase of pH from pH ca. 1. The compounds (vide Experimental) isolated at pH ca. 1 contain $\text{Sn}^{4+} : \text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-} = 1 : 2$. The composition of the isolated compounds at this pH indicates the existence of $[\text{SnO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]^{2-}$ ion in the solid state. It appears that when oxalic acid is used for masking tin(IV), it remains in aqueous solution in the above form or as $[\text{Sn}(\text{OH})_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]^{2-}$ ion. The isolation of a potassium compound⁵ containing $[\text{SnS}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]^{2-}$ ion by passing H_2S into a tin(IV) solution containing excess oxalic acid supports the existence of an oxo-oxalatostannate species as suggested above. Since ethylenediamine bisoxalatostannate $(\text{enH}_2)-[\text{SnO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$, was obtained in the anhydrous condition, and $\text{K}_4[\text{Sn}_2\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_5] \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ could be dehydrated completely in vacuum over P_4O_{10} to yield anhydrous product, the oxalatostannates, which could be formulated either as oxo- or hydroxooxalatostannates, have been represented as oxo-compounds. Besides, the ir spectra of these compounds do not show band at 860 cm^{-1} characteristic for $\text{Sn}-\text{OH}^6$.

The methods used by previous workers² for the preparation of potassium heptaoxalatodistannate $\text{K}_6[\text{Sn}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_7] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{A})$ involved several steps, whereas the method described in this communication for its preparation is a rapid, easy single step process. Although doubt was expressed³ about the identity of the above compound, but the isolation of the same compound also through a new procedure and its recrystallisation both from water and from

oxalic acid solution bear proof of its existence. The isolation of rubidium, sodium and 1,10-phenanthroline heptaoxalatodistannates corroborates the existence of $[\text{Sn}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_7]^{6-}$ ion. Additional evidences in favour of the above ion have been rendered by the isolation of the compounds of the formula $\text{K}_6[\text{Sn}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_6\text{F}_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{K}_6[\text{Sn}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_5\text{F}_4] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ through stepwise replacement of oxalate ion by fluoride⁷ from the compound A and by the isolation of potassium oxo-oxalatodistannates. Further, the trisoxalato compound $\text{K}_2\text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3 \cdot 1/2\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{B})$, could not be obtained directly from $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ and SnCl_4 in the presence or absence of oxalic acid, but the compound A was obtained instead under both the above conditions. It might be that the compound A being somewhat less soluble than the compound B gets crystallised out first (vide solubility data of the two compounds).

The ir spectra of the various oxalatostannates showed bands at 1400, 795–830 and $480-530 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are characteristic bands for the chelated oxalate groups^{4,8}. Another diagnostic band for the chelated oxalate group is found in the region 1620–1660 cm^{-1} , but this band and another one found at 1400 cm^{-1} in the spectra for ammonium, hexaamminecobalt(III) and various cationic organic base oxalatostannates may also⁸ be due to $\delta_{\text{H}-\text{O}-\text{H}}$ or δ_{NH_3} and ν_{NH} respectively. The bands found at 3200–3500 cm^{-1} are possibly due to ν_{OH} mode of lattice water or ν_{NH} . The bands around 475, 550, 660 and 900 cm^{-1} are probably due⁴ to $\nu_{\text{Sn}-\text{O}}$. Since these results suggest the presence of only chelated oxalate groups in the bis- and trisoxalatostannates, hexacoordination for tin(IV) in these compounds can be assumed. But in the heptaoxalatodistannates, probably three bidentate oxalate groups are linked to each of two tin atoms and the rest oxalate group remains as bridge (bidentate or tetradentate) in between two Sn atoms whilst in ammonium tetraoxalatostannate all the oxalato groups are bidentate.

The TG of potassium compound $\text{K}_6[\text{Sn}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_7] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, upto 500°, showed four steps starting at 100, 250, 340 and 490° (Fig. 1) which suggested the successive formation of anhydrous compound $\text{K}_6[\text{Sn}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_7]$, oxo-oxalatotin compounds $\text{K}_6[\text{Sn}_2\text{O}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_5]$ and $\text{K}_6[\text{Sn}_2\text{O}_4(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3]$ as intermediates; the end-product appears to be a mixture of K_2SnO_3 and $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$. The formation of these products was supported by chemical analysis, ir data and chemical properties of the products. TG studies of potassium oxo-oxalatostannates did not show the formation of stable intermediate.

Fig. 1

The TG curve of the rubidium compound, $\text{Rb}_6[\text{Sn}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_7] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was similar to that of the potassium compound. But the corresponding steps were observed at lower temperatures. The TG curve of the sodium compound, $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_4[\text{Sn}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_7] \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ did not show the formation of stable intermediate even upto 500° . The TG curve of $\text{K}_2[\text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3] \cdot 1/2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ showed successive formation of anhydrous compound at 70° , $\text{K}_2[\text{SnO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$ at 230° , $\text{K}_2[\text{SnO}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)]$ at 260° and K_2SnO_3 at 360° .

The ammonium compound, $(\text{NH}_4)_4[\text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ decomposed rapidly from 80° and yielded SnO_2 at 330° . The various cationic amine oxalatoxostannates yielded SnO_2 at the temperature range $250\text{--}500^\circ$.

Experimental

Hexaamminecobalt(III) nitrate, sodium hexahydroxostannate and potassium thiooxalatoxostannate were prepared by reported methods described^{5,9}.

The chemical analyses were carried out by standard methods¹⁰ (Table 1). TGA data and ir spectra were recorded as before⁵. pH was measured with an Elico LI 10T pH meter.

Potassium oxalatoxostannate tetrahydrate, $\text{K}_6[\text{Sn}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_7] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was precipitated (8 g) on adding a solution (10 ml) of tin(IV) chloride hydrate (7 g) to a solution (25 ml) of potassium oxalate (11.5 g) (pH of mixture ca. 5). It could be recrystallised from water or from oxalic acid solution; solubility of the compound, 5.06 g/100 ml. Rubidium oxalatoxostannate tetrahydrate $\text{Rb}_6[\text{Sn}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_7] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained in the second crop of crystals as above through fractional crystallisation in a desiccator. Disodium acid oxalatoxostannate $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_4[\text{Sn}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_7] \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained by dissolving sodium hexahydroxostannate in a solution of oxalic acid and then evaporating as above. 1,10-Phenanthroline oxalatoxostannate hydrate $(\text{phen H}_2)_3[\text{Sn}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_7] \cdot 14\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained through addition of 1,10-phenanthroline oxalate to a solution of potassium oxalatoxostannate and evaporating the mixture (pH 2.1).

Potassium trisoxalatoxostannate hemihydrate, $\text{K}_2[\text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3] \cdot 1/2\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Potassium oxalate (0.253 g) was

added to a solution of potassium thiooxalatoxostannate $\text{K}_2[\text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3] \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.0 g) and then a solution of silver nitrate (0.466 g) was added dropwise, filtered, and the filtrate (pH ca. 3) was evaporated under reduced pressure to crystallisation (1.0 g); solubility of the compound, 5.5 g/100 ml. The pH of its aqueous solution was ca. 3. The compound could be recrystallised from water and on dehydration over P_4O_{10} in a vacuum desiccator it yielded the anhydrous compound.

Guanidinium trisoxalatoxostannate hydrate, $(\text{guH})_2[\text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained in the second crop of crystals through fractional crystallisation of a mixture of potassium oxalatoxostannate and guanidinium oxalate. Hexaamminecobalt(III) hydrogen tris-oxalatoxostannate hydrate, $\text{H}[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][\text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3] \cdot 17\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained as an orange crystalline precipitate on adding a solution of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6](\text{NO}_3)_3$ (0.6 g) to a solution containing $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (4 g) and $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 g) (pH of mixture 6). Hexaamminecobalt(III) oxohydroxobisoxalatoxostannate pentahydrate, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][\text{Sn}(\text{O})(\text{OH})(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained as orange crystalline precipitate on adding a solution of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6](\text{NO}_3)_3$ to a mixture of $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and oxalic acid (pH of mixture 0.75).

Ammonium tetrakisoxalatoxostannate trihydrate, $(\text{NH}_4)_4[\text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_4] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Hydrated tin(IV) oxide was dissolved in an excess of oxalic acid solution and ammonia was added to it till precipitation. It was filtered and the filtrate was fractionally crystallised as before. The compound, which was highly soluble, was obtained in the fifth crop of crystals.

Bisoxalatoxostannates of some organic base cations, $(\text{BH})_2[\text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where B = pyridine (py), 2-aminopyridine (2-ampy), 1,10-phenanthroline (phen), quinoline (qu), 2,2', bipyridyl (bipy), 1/2 ethylenediamine (en), and $x = 3, 1, 1, 2, 3$ and 0 respectively. *General method*: For the preparation of these compounds, a solution of amine neutralised partly by oxalic acid was added to a solution of tin(IV) chloride and oxalic acid (the mole ratio of amine : tin : oxalic acid = 2 : 1 : 3) with stirring. The pyridinium, 2-aminopyridinium and ethylenediaminium compounds were obtained through evaporation of the mixtures in vacuo in a desiccator, while other compounds precipitated immediately on adding the amine solution (pH of mother liquors 0.05–0.65). The compounds were found insoluble in common organic solvents.

Potassium hexakisoxalatoxostannate tetrahydrate, $\text{K}_6[\text{Sn}_2\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_6] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared by adding silver nitrate to an aqueous solution of $\text{K}_6[\text{Sn}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_7] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the mole ratio 2 : 1, filtered and the filtrate was evaporated as above. Potassium pentakisoxalatoxostannate hydrate, $\text{K}_4[\text{Sn}_2\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_5] \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained as above by adding $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ to an aqueous solution of $\text{K}_6[\text{Sn}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_7] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the mole ratio 3 : 1.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR OXALATOSTANNATES

Compd ^a	N	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		Alkali metal/Co
		Sn	C ₂ O ₄	
K ₆ [Sn ₂ (C ₂ O ₄) ₇].4H ₂ O	—	21.10 (20.47)	53.22 53.13	19.98 20.18
Rb ₆ [Sn ₂ (C ₂ O ₄) ₇].4H ₂ O	—	16.14 (16.50)	42.84 42.83	35.50 35.65
Na ₂ H ₄ [Sn ₂ (C ₂ O ₄) ₇].12H ₂ O	—	21.29 (21.20)	55.15 55.03	4.39 4.10
(phenH ₃) ₃ [Sn ₂ (C ₂ O ₄) ₇].14H ₂ O	5.05 (5.09)	14.76 14.40	37.41 37.37	—
K ₂ [Sn(C ₂ O ₄) ₃].1/2 H ₂ O	—	25.51 (25.26)	56.64 56.21	16.74 16.60
(guH ₂) ₂ [Sn(C ₂ O ₄) ₃].6H ₂ O	13.48 (13.75)	19.64 19.43	45.32 43.11	—
H[Co(NH ₃) ₆][Sn(C ₂ O ₄) ₃].17H ₂ O	6.80 (6.80)	19.69 19.24	42.87 42.81	—
[Co(NH ₃) ₆][SnO(OH)(C ₂ O ₄) ₂].5H ₂ O	15.00 (14.98)	21.68 21.17	31.22 31.39	10.65 10.51
(NH ₄) ₄ [Sn(C ₂ O ₄) ₄].3H ₂ O	9.28 (9.38)	19.72 19.89	59.47 58.99	—
(pyH ₂) ₂ [SnO(C ₂ O ₄) ₂].3H ₂ O	5.96 (5.33)	22.04 22.62	33.59 33.59	—
(2-ampyH ₂) ₂ [SnO(C ₂ O ₄) ₂].H ₂ O	11.11 (10.79)	21.91 22.88	34.26 33.93	—
(phenH ₂) ₂ [SnO(C ₂ O ₄) ₂].H ₂ O	8.10 (8.10)	16.72 17.18	26.39 25.48	—
(quH ₂) ₂ [SnO(C ₂ O ₄) ₂].2H ₂ O	4.32 (4.61)	19.46 19.55	29.34 28.99	—
(bipyH ₂) ₂ [SnO(C ₂ O ₄) ₂].3H ₂ O	7.45	17.65	25.59	—
(enH ₂) ₂ [SnO(C ₂ O ₄) ₂]	7.69 (7.51)	30.38 31.84	47.98 47.21	26.54 —
K ₆ [Sn ₂ O(C ₂ O ₄) ₆].4H ₂ O	—	21.44 (21.83)	49.01 48.55	21.09 21.52
K ₄ [Sn ₂ O(C ₂ O ₄) ₅].9H ₂ O	—	23.30 (23.47)	43.36 43.50	15.59 15.42

phen = *o*-phenanthroline, gu = guanidine, py = pyridine, 2-ampy = 2-aminopyridine, qu = quinoline, bipy = 2,2'-bipyridyl, en = ethylenediamine.

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